

Understanding the relationship between parental involvement and self-efficacy: A systematic review 2015-2024

Transparency Standards for Systematic Reviews

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1. Introduction

1.1. Rationale

Parental involvement plays a pivotal role in children's development, significantly impacting academic performance and well-being (Jeynes, 2009; Yap et al., 2014). Within this framework, self-efficacy, an individual's belief in their ability to achieve goals (Bandura, 1997), emerges as a crucial mediator. While research consistently demonstrates a positive association between parental involvement and children's self-efficacy (Hoover-Dempsey et al., 2005), the underlying mechanisms of this relationship remain inadequately understood.

This lack of clarity stems from several key challenges. First, the multifaceted nature of parental involvement, encompassing diverse behaviors and contexts (e.g., school-based vs. home-based, cognitive vs. behavioral), necessitates a nuanced understanding of its impact on self-efficacy (Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1994). Second, the available studies employ varying definitions and measures of parental involvement and self-efficacy, hindering direct comparisons and a comprehensive understanding of their interplay. Third, parental involvement and self-efficacy likely vary across developmental stages, sociodemographic contexts, and cultural backgrounds. Fourth, while research often emphasizes the link between parental involvement and academic achievement, the mediating role of self-efficacy in this relationship warrants further investigation (Caprara et al., 2011; Ferraces Otero et al., 2021).

To address these limitations, a systematic review is crucial to: (1) integrate findings from diverse studies, clarifying which specific parental behaviors most strongly influence children's self-efficacy; (2) explore the pathways through which parental involvement

impacts self-efficacy, such as through fostering intrinsic motivation, promoting self-regulated learning, or enhancing emotional regulation; (3) examine how the relationship between parental involvement and self-efficacy varies across different age groups, socioeconomic backgrounds, and cultural contexts; and (4) provide evidence-based guidance for the development of programs and interventions that empower parents to foster their children's self-efficacy.

This systematic review addresses these critical knowledge gaps, significantly improving educational outcomes by providing educators and parents with a deeper understanding of how to effectively support children's academic and personal growth. On the other hand, it will contribute to advancing research by identifying areas for future research and refining our understanding of the complex interplay between parental involvement and child development.

References

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1.2. Objectives

The primary objective of this review is to provide a reliable foundation that can advance, at a theoretical level, the development of an explanatory model of the relationship between parental involvement and the self-efficacy perceived by their children. At a practical level, it aims to inform decision-making regarding changes, reforms, or proposals that can be designed and implemented to improve the studied reality.

2. Methods

2.1. Eligibility criteria

The inclusion criteria we followed for the selection of the manuscripts were as follows:

- Publication date: January 2015 and May 2024
- Language: Spanish and English
- Field: Psychoeducation
- Full-text availability (open access articles, institutional accessibility, and author's copy)
- Sample: Early elementary through high school students and/or their parents
- Measures: Children's self-efficacy
- Measures: Parental involvement
- Measures within the academic context
- Type of study: Experimental and quasi-experimental studies

2.2. Information sources

After checking against some other systematic reviews in the field of education and psychology, the intended information sources will be the following electronic databases: (1) PsycInfo, (2) ERIC, (3) Web of Science, (4) Scopus, and (5) Dialnet.

All databases and the full texts of articles identified will be accessed via the library subscriptions of either the University of A Coruña or the University of Santiago de

Compostela. Articles not accessible through subscriptions will be obtained from other online search engines (e.g., ResearchGate, Google Scholar) or publishing authors of those works.

2.3. Search strategy

The systematic search used the following terms: “perceived parental behavior”, “perceived parental involvement”, and “parental involvement”, combined with “perceived self-efficacy”. The search was also conducted using the Spanish translations of the terms, as several databases primarily feature documentation in Spanish.

2.4. Selection process

The article selection process for this systematic review was structured across several stages. Initially, a comprehensive search of relevant databases was conducted using predefined search terms and filters to identify potential articles. Subsequently, a rigorous screening process was implemented. This involved a preliminary review of article titles and abstracts to select potentially eligible studies. Duplicates and articles not available in English or Spanish were removed at this stage. Exclusion criteria were then applied to eliminate studies that did not align with the research objectives, had inappropriate samples, or focused on specific curricular areas.

In the third stage, a thorough review of the full-text articles was conducted to determine their final inclusion. Studies were excluded due to characteristics that did not fit the review's scope, the use of measures that were not within the academic context, or a mismatch between study variables and research objectives. Documentary analysis was employed as a technique for evaluating each article, with an information matrix used to organize the data. Any discrepancies encountered during the pre-selection and selection phases were resolved through discussions among all review authors to ensure consensus. Finally, the exclusion criteria were re-applied after the analysis to ensure the final set of included studies met the rigorous criteria established for the review.

2.5. Data collection process

Four reviewers worked independently to collect data from each report. A fifth reviewer helped to resolve disagreements between data collectors. For each article, reviewers extracted data on the date, country, and type of study, research goal(s), sample characteristics (gender, age/academic stage, nationality of children and parents), measures of parental involvement and self-efficacy, instruments used for their assessment, and the main results

related to the variables of interest. All the information was included on a shared table until the data collectors' agreement was reached.

3. Results

3.1. Data analysis and synthesis

The study characteristics that were assessed are: Study design, sample characteristics (gender, age/academic stage, nationality of children and parents), parental involvement measures, self-efficacy measures, data collection instruments, and data analysis methods.

The planned analysis for this review employs a descriptive synthesis approach. This method is well-suited for systematic reviews that aim to comprehensively understand a phenomenon (relationship between parental involvement and student self-efficacy) across diverse studies with potentially different research designs and methods. The following steps were followed for data synthesis:

1. Coding and Categorization: Data extracted from each study was coded based on the type(s) of parental involvement and the dimension(s) of self-efficacy assessed by each paper. We then established categories for each of them:
 - a. Parental involvement:
 - i. Parental volitional actions:
 1. Parental monitoring
 2. Promotion of learning at home
 3. Home-school communication and interest
 4. Task support
 5. Communication and interest in children.
 - ii. Parental motivational actions:
 1. Parental support
 2. Aspirations and expectations
 3. Parental affect
 - iii. Parenting style:
 1. Parental control
 2. Parental autonomy support
 - b. Self-efficacy:
 - i. Social self-efficacy
 - ii. Emotional self-efficacy
 - iii. Academic self-efficacy

1. Ability to achieve success
 2. Self-efficacy for cognitive management
 3. Self-efficacy for motivational management
 4. Self-efficacy for context management
 5. Self-efficacy for behavioral management
2. Based on the identified themes and categories, we described the relationship between parental involvement and self-efficacy attending to the results observed for each of the categories identified across the studies. This description considered the magnitude of the relationship between the variables and the effects of each type of parental involvement on self-efficacy in each paper.
 3. We then compared and contrasted the findings across studies, exploring similarities and variations in their results. To this purpose, we considered factors like the age and gender of the participants (children and parents) and who reported the information on parental involvement.
 4. The final analysis and synthesis integrate the findings from different studies.

4. Biases

4.1. Risk of bias/trustworthiness of individual studies

To assess the quality and potential bias of the included studies, we used Cochrane (Higgins et al., 2022). In particular, we pay attention to the research design, sampling, data collection methods, data analysis procedures, ethical considerations, and the indexation of the journals in which the documents have been published.

Higgins, J. P. T., Thomas, J., Chandler, J., Cumpston, M., Li, T., Page, M. J., & Welch, V. A. (Eds.) (2022). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* (version 6.3). Wiley-Blackwell. <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current>

4.2. Meta-biases

To address meta-biases, we conducted a comprehensive search strategy employing a variety of keywords and search strategies to capture a broad range of relevant studies. We clearly outlined the criteria for including and excluding studies to minimize any bias. Furthermore, four reviewers independently conducted the data selection and extraction following a previously structured protocol.

This review includes any articles published in languages the authors are fluent in (Spanish and English). It is an explicit attempt to exclude any studies published in any other

language, since AI translators may not be able to provide translation accurate enough for any further assessment in the review. Any attempt to mitigate any language bias could be addressed in future research.

5. Other information

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5.2. Availability of data

Along this document, we have made publicly available under the same DOI the included and excluded studies (Supplemental Table S1 and S2), the quality assessment of the included articles (Supplemental Table S3), and a table showing the content clusters according to the variables of interest in this systematic review (Supplemental Table S4).